

Using Phase Equilibrium Theory to Calculate Solubility of γ -Oryzanol in Supercritical CO₂

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Abstract—Even its content is rich in antioxidants γ -oryzanol, rice bran is not used properly as functional food. This research aims to (1) extract γ -oryzanol; (2) determine the solubility of γ -oryzanol in supercritical CO₂ based on phase equilibrium theory; and (3) study the effect of process variables on solubility. Extraction experiments were carried out for rice bran (5 g) at various extraction pressures, temperatures and reaction times. The flowrate of supercritical fluid through the extraction vessel was 25 g/min. The extracts were collected and analysed with high-pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC). The conclusion based on the experiments are as: (1) The highest experimental solubility was 0.303 mcg/mL RBO at T= 60°C, P= 90 atm, t= 30 min; (2) Solubility of γ -oryzanol was influenced by pressure and temperature. As the pressure and temperature increase, the solubility increases; (3) The solubility data of supercritical extraction can be successfully determined using phase equilibrium theory. Meanwhile, tocopherol was found and slightly investigated in this work.

Keywords—Rice bran, solubility, supercritical CO₂, γ -oryzanol.

I. INTRODUCTION

RICE is one of the important agricultural crops in Indonesia. One of by-products from the process of milling rice is rice bran [1]. The utilisation of rice bran is not optimal i.e. for animal livestock, ash and fuel reboiler, and sometimes casually discarded [1]. The rice bran is rich in nutrients so it may be useful as high quality health food supplement. [2], [3].

Rice bran oil can be produced by extraction [4]. Rice bran oil contains anti-oxidants i.e. tocopherol, tocotrienol and γ -oryzanol. Among them, γ -oryzanol is reported as a powerful antioxidant that plays an important role in the metabolism of fat in the body, and is believed to prevent the coronary heart diseases and cancer [3].

The considered method to extract oil for food is the supercritical CO₂ extraction [5]. Mostly, parameters observed in the supercritical extraction are temperature and pressure [6].

The equation of state (EOS) is widely used to determine the solubility of solid in supercritical fluid. The solubility is predicted as a function of temperature and pressure. One of the EOS models that most commonly used to study the behavior of equilibrium is the Peng-Robinson (PR-EOS) model [7], [8].

A. Peng-Robinson Model

$$p = \frac{RT}{v-b} - \frac{a(T)}{v(v+b)+b(v-b)} \quad (1)$$

with

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$$b = 0,07780 \frac{RT_c}{P_c} \quad (2)$$

$$a(T) = a(T_c)\alpha(T) \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha(T) = \left[1 + \beta \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{T}{T_c}} \right) \right]^2 \quad (4)$$

$$a(T_c) = 0,45724 \frac{(RT_c)^2}{P_c} \quad (5)$$

where R is the gas constant, T_c is the critical temperature and P_c is pressure.

The solubility of pure solid, such as A, in supercritical fluid can be determined by using the equilibrium theory. Terms of the conditional in equilibrium between pure solid and supercritical fluid (SCF) in extraction process is expressed by

$$f_A^S = f_A^{SCF} \quad (6)$$

with f_A^S = fugacity of component (A) in a solid phase, f_A^{SCF} = fugacity of component (A) in a supercritical phase.

For pure components:

$$\ln \left(\frac{f}{p} \right) = \frac{1}{RT} \int_{p=0}^{p=p} \left(v - \frac{RT}{p} \right) dp \quad (7)$$

Thus, it can be expressed in the form of

$$\ln \left(\frac{f}{p} \right) = \frac{1}{RT} \left[\int_{v=v}^{v=\infty} \left(p - \frac{RT}{v} \right) dv - RT \ln z + RT(z-1) \right] \quad (8)$$

with

$$z = \frac{pv}{RT} \quad (9)$$

To calculate fugacity of pure solid, (7) can be arranged in the form of;

$$\ln \frac{f^s}{p} = \frac{1}{RT} \left[\int_{p=0}^{p=p^{sat}} \left(v - \frac{RT}{p} \right) dp + \int_{p=p^{sat}}^{p=p} \left(v^s - \frac{RT}{p} \right) dp \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\ln \frac{f^s}{p} = \frac{1}{RT} \left[RT \ln \frac{f^{sat}}{p^{sat}} + \int_{p=p^{sat}}^{p=p} v^s dp - RT \ln \frac{p}{p^{sat}} \right] \quad (11)$$

$$RT \ln \frac{f^s}{p} = \left[RT \ln \frac{f^{\text{sat}}}{p^{\text{sat}}} + \int_{p^{\text{sat}}}^{p=p} v^s dp - RT \ln \frac{p}{p^{\text{sat}}} \right] \quad (12)$$

$$f^s = p^{\text{sat}} \phi^{\text{sat}} \exp \left(\int_{p^{\text{sat}}}^{p=p} \frac{v^s}{RT} dp \right) \quad (13)$$

with

$$\phi^{\text{sat}} = \frac{f^{\text{sat}}}{p^{\text{sat}}} \quad (14)$$

For solute A, then (13) will be;

$$f_A^s = p_A^{\text{sat}} \phi_A^{\text{sat}} \exp \left(\int_{p_A^{\text{sat}}}^{p=p} \frac{v_A^s}{RT} dp \right) \quad (15)$$

Fugacity on supercritical phase is;

$$f_A^{\text{SCF}} = \phi_A y_A P \quad (16)$$

substitute (15) and (16) to (6), then (6) can be re-written as;

$$p_A^{\text{sat}} \phi_A^{\text{sat}} \exp \left(\int_{p_A^{\text{sat}}}^{p=p} \frac{v_A^s}{RT} dp \right) = \phi_A y_A P \quad (17)$$

Then,

$$y_A = \frac{p_A^{\text{sat}} \phi_A^{\text{sat}} \exp \left(\int_{p_A^{\text{sat}}}^{p=p} \frac{v_A^s}{RT} dp \right)}{\phi_A P} \quad (18)$$

If

$$E = \frac{\phi_A^{\text{sat}}}{\phi_A} \exp \left(\int_{p_A^{\text{sat}}}^{p=p} \frac{v_A^s}{RT} dp \right) \quad (19)$$

Equation (18) can be re-written as;

$$y_A = \frac{p_A^{\text{sat}}}{p} E \quad (20)$$

with y_A = solubility (solut) in the phase supercritical, p_A^{sat} = the saturation pressure of component (A).

Equation (20) can be used to calculate the solubility of γ -oryzanol in supercritical CO_2 .

II.METHODOLOGY

A. Materials

Rice bran (IR 64 rice varieties with a water content of less than 10% (w/w) was supplied from Central Rice Production in Central Java, Indonesia. High purity of 99.98% Carbon dioxide (CO_2) was purchased from Gas Depo Industry, Indonesia.

B. Experimental

Research procedures are such as in Fig. 1. Process parameters observed in this study are the temperature (40-60°C), pressure (80-90 atm) and reaction time (5-30) minutes. To quantify the amount of γ -oryzanol, the liquid product was analysed by HPLC.

Fig. 1 Flow diagram of experimental procedures

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Exploratory experiments to determine the solubility of γ -oryzanol were performed at 50°C and 90 atm, using rice bran intake of 5 g. A typical concentration profile showed solubility is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 The solubility of γ -oryzanol

To investigate the effect of process variables on the solubility of γ -Oryzanol in supercritical CO_2 , 20 experiments

were conducted in a batch reactor set up. Three independent variables, as shown in Table I, were explored and the solubility of γ -Oryzanol was taken as the dependent variables. The results are provided in Table I.

TABLE I
OVERVIEW OF EXPERIMENTS

Run	reaction time (min)	pressure (atm)	Temperature, (°C)	y γ -oryzanol (mcg/mL rice bran oil)
1	15	85	40	0.067
2	30	90	60	0.303
3	15	90	50	0.188
4	15	85	60	0.115
5	30	90	40	0.211
6	15	85	50	0.108
7	5	80	40	0.020
8	5	90	60	0.101
9	15	85	50	0.108
10	30	80	40	0.060
11	15	80	50	0.072
12	15	85	50	0.108
13	5	90	40	0.090
14	15	85	50	0.108
15	30	80	60	0.184
16	5	85	50	0.054
17	15	85	50	0.108
18	30	85	50	0.214
19	15	85	50	0.108
20	5	80	60	0.050

Based on Table I, the highest solubility of γ -oryzanol is 0.303 mcg/mL rice bran oil (entry 2,) and was gained at reaction time of 30 min, pressure of 90 atm at 60°C. The parity plots described in Fig. 3 indicate a good agreement between the experimental and predicted data. The effect of process variable on solubility can be illustrated in Fig. 4. It is obviously drawn that pressure and temperature has profound effect. As pressure increases, the solubility increases. Higher pressure and temperature lead to higher diffusivity and density of fluid. It makes the supercritical CO₂ strongly pushing out the oil from the rice bran matrix.

Fig. 3 Parity plot of γ -oryzanol

Fig. 4 Effect of temperature and pressure on solubility γ -oryzanol in supercritical CO₂

Herein this study, we also found the tocopherol content in extracted rice bran oil. This finding (in Table II) shows the relationship between reaction time, pressure and temperature to yield of tocopherol.

TABLE II
OVERVIEW ON TOCOPHEROL CONTENT

Run	reaction time (min)	pressure (atm)	Temperature, (°C)	y γ -tocopherol (mcg/mL rice bran oil)
1	15	85	40	0.015
2	30	90	60	0.050
3	15	85	60	0.026
4	30	90	40	0.029
5	15	85	50	0.016
6	5	80	40	0.008
7	5	90	60	0.011
8	15	85	50	0.016
9	30	80	40	0.019
10	15	80	50	0.009
11	15	85	50	0.016
12	5	90	40	0.010
13	15	85	50	0.016
14	30	80	60	0.030
15	5	85	50	0.009
16	15	85	50	0.016
17	30	85	50	0.028
18	15	85	50	0.224
19	5	80	60	0.016

Fig. 5 Parity plot of tocopherol

Fig. 6 Effect of temperature and pressure on solubility tocopherol in supercritical CO₂

Table II informs that the highest yield of tocopherol is 0.224 mcg/mL rice bran oil (entry 18) at condition of T=50°C, P=85 atm and t=15 min. Meanwhile, Fig 5 shows that experimental values fit with predicted values. The effect of temperature and pressure on yield of tocopherol is explicitly stated in Fig. 6.

IV. CONCLUSION

An in-depth experimental study on the determination of γ -oryzanol solubility in supercritical was conducted in a batch supercritical reactor. The highest experimental solubility (0.303 mcg/mL RBO) was obtained at 60°C, pressure of 90 atm, a reaction time of 30 min.

This work also concludes that (1) the solubility of γ -oryzanol become greater with increasing temperature and pressure; (2) the solubility data on the extraction of solid-supercritical fluid in this research can be obtained based on the concept of phase equilibrium.

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